

ORGANIZING MATHEMATICS LESSONS USING ICT

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Abstract.

In this article, ICT for mathematics lessons in elementary grades the effect of organizing and elementary school students' mathematics interest in science, mastery of educational materials and mathematics to organize club trainings in order to further develop their knowledge The significance of this is discussed and recommendations are made. It is new in mathematics classes ways to achieve high results as a result of wide use of pedagogical technologies are highlighted given

Key words.

Mathematics lessons in elementary grades, extracurricular training, ICT, pedagogical technology, student knowledge and practical skills development methods.

Introduction

The level of development of society, the transformation of our time into the information age, young people are mature, quick to assess the situation, correct in any situation and to prepare a competent professional who can make rational decisions it is not enough to teach based only on traditional methods. New pedagogy and in the organization of classes based on information technologies mentally and physically mature students, with a wide spiritual outlook, any a competent person who can react to the situation with his common sense the opportunity to educate individuals is wide. Nowadays, modern computers are used in general education schools improving the possibilities of using technologies, education full use of the possibilities of modern technologies in the process it is no secret that its importance is recognized.

Main part

Almost all schools in our country have modern computers and equipped with telecommunication technologies. And this, in turn a new approach to the professional activity of primary school teachers requires. Mathematics lessons with the help of modern information technologies In the organization, the teacher first:

- the purpose of the lesson;
- ways to achieve the goal;
- methods of presenting educational materials;
- teaching methods; - types of educational assignments; -questions for discussion; - ways of organizing discussions and debates; - improvement of communication methods with the help of ICT should pay attention to others. Then the intended goal will be achieved.

Only mathematical knowledge in the course of class or group activities not only given, but also the essence of our national traditions and values knowledge, skills and competencies are developed. Different slides or other innovative technologies compared to the lecture It is effective to influence students with Students pay attention to the lesson ICT to focus, arouse interest in science in them and increase their activity is the most convenient tool. The teacher performs the following tasks through the use of ICT can do: - through the use of multimedia technologies in primary classes students' interest in science increases;

- this method of education improves students' thinking abilities activates and increases the efficiency of learning material develops; - enables easy understanding of a process that is difficult to understand; - students to search and find materials through independent research perform certain research works by finding answers to problematic issues creates an opportunity to increase; - mastering a new subject, solving examples and problems, educational material independent familiarization with , quick execution of issues such as selection and analysis creates conditions for; A lesson and a club to carry out such tasks training in different formats: video, audio, slide, quiz test, diagrams, can be presented in charts and musical forms.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the use of ICT in the educational process is above only if it is organized on the basis of requirements, the quality of education will increase. If we apply the recommendations given above in the course of our work we can certainly achieve high results. Educate the young generation in all aspects, We will contribute to his education. Primary school teacher lays the foundation of knowledge. The stronger the foundation, the better students are people who make a worthy contribution to the development of our country they reach Our main goal is to educate such people is considered

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